

A Review of Biotic Interactions and Taxon Names Found in `globalbioticinteractions/seinet` hash://md5/9ba4ec70e4b75d9d63c904eb2167fd1b

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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/seinet/issues>

2025-04-13

Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/seinet`, has fingerprint hash://md5/9ba4ec70e4b75d9d63c904eb2167fd1b, is 308MiB in size and contains 993,128 interaction with 4 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 19,266 primary taxon (e.g., *Agave chrysantha*) and 65,970 associated taxon (e.g., *Pinus ponderosa*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review:

ARIZ DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of Arizona Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/ARIZ_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z ASC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Deaver Herbarium (Northern Arizona University) https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/ASC_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z ASDM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Arizona-Sonora Desert Museum https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/ASDM_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z ASU-CCH DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Cochise County Herbarium - Arizona State University https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/ASU-CCH_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z ASU-Plants DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Arizona State University Vascular Plant Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/ASU-Plants_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z AWC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Arizona Western College Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/AWC_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z BLM-LCDO DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Bureau of Land Management, Las Cruces District Office https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/BLM-LCDO_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z BLM-NM DwC-

Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Bureau of Land Management - New Mexico State Offices https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/BLM-NM_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z BTA-Plants DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Boyce Thompson Arboretum https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/BTA-Plants_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z DES DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Desert Botanical Garden Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/DES_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z ENMU DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Eastern New Mexico University Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/ENMU_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z KAIB DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Kaibab National Forest Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/KAIB_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z MNA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Museum of Northern Arizona https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/MNA_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z NAVA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Navajo Nation Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/NAVA_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z NEON-APLC-HVCH DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for ASU-NEON Aquatic Plant, Bryophyte, and Macroalgae Collection (Herbarium Vouchers [Clip Harvests]) https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/NEON-APLC-HVCH_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z NEON-APLC-HVPC DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for ASU-NEON Aquatic Plant, Bryophyte, and Macroalgae Collection (Herbarium Vouchers [Point Counts]) https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/NEON-APLC-HVPC_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z NEON-APLC-HVSS DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for ASU-NEON Aquatic Plant, Bryophyte, and Macroalgae Collection (Herbarium Vouchers [Standard Sampling]) https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/NEON-APLC-HVSS_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z NEON-TPLC-HV DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for ASU-NEON Terrestrial Plant Collection (Herbarium Vouchers) https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/NEON-TPLC-HV_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z NHI DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Natural History Institute Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/NHI_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z SFBG DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Santa Fe Botanical Garden Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/SFBG_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z SJNM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for San Juan College Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/SJNM_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z SNM DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Western New Mexico University, Dale A. Zimmerman Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/SNM_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z SWRS DwC-Archive | Darwin Core

Archive for Southwestern Research Station https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/SWRS_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z UNM-Vascular Plants DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for University of New Mexico Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/UNM-VascularPlants_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z USFS-COCAZ DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Coconino National Forest Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/USFS-COCAZ_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z USFS-GILA DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Gila National Forest Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/USFS-GILA_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z USFS-PNF DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Prescott National Forest Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/USFS-PNF_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z USFS-SWRH DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for Southwestern Regional Forest Service Herbarium https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/USFS-SWRH_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z USFS-TNF DwC-Archive | Darwin Core Archive for US Forest Service - Tonto National Forest https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/content/dwca/USFS-TNF_DwC-A.zip 2025-04-12T10:32:47.444Z hash://md5/9ba4ec70e4b75d9d63c904eb2167fd1b

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/seinet> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.10.1
elton	0.15.9
nomer	0.5.13
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 308MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/seinet

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/seinet\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/seinet\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/seinet\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/seinet`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/seinet`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/seinet`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/seinet`)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned Preston (Elliott et al. 2025) archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/seinet`, has fingerprint hash://md5/9ba4ec70e4b75d9d63c904eb2167fd1b, is 308MiB in size and contains 993,128 interaction with 4 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 19,266 primary taxon (e.g., *Agave chrysantha*) and 65,970 associated taxon (e.g., *Pinus ponderosa*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv and

tsv archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Acalypha neomexicana	adjacentTo	N. facing slope	https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/collections/indiv
Acalypha neomexicana	adjacentTo	dry	https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/collections/indiv
Acalypha neomexicana	adjacentTo	grassy slope in pine forest	https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/collections/indiv
Acalypha neomexicana	adjacentTo	roadside in pine forest	https://swbiodiversity.org/seinet/collections/indiv

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	962022
adjacentTo	31075
hasHost	28
eats	3

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Agave chrysantha	5198
Agave palmeri	4009
Erigeron divergens	2519
Plantago patagonica	2230
Opuntia phaeacantha	2142
Bouteloua gracilis	2109
Cryptantha barbiger	2023
Bouteloua curtispindula	2010
Erodium cicutarium	1894
Phacelia distans	1847
Pinus edulis	1826
Lepidium lasiocarpum	1814

sourceTaxonName	count
Elymus elymoides	1745
Agave verdensis	1736
Silene antirrhina	1667
Aristida adscensionis	1656
Yucca baccata	1621
Descurainia pinnata	1619
Bromus rubens	1560

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Pinus ponderosa	9273
Gutierrezia sarothrae	9135
Pinus edulis	8175
Larrea tridentata	7922
Bouteloua gracilis	6493
Prosopis velutina	6299
Acacia greggii	6072
Opuntia engelmannii	5822
Juniperus osteosperma	5818
Quercus gambelii	5649
Encelia farinosa	5462
Bouteloua curtipendula	5304
Fouquieria splendens	4804
Juniperus deppeana	4654
Juniperus	4636
Quercus turbinella	4467
Yucca baccata	4430
Carnegiea gigantea	3944
Ephedra	3915

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Opuntia engelmannii	266
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Gutierrezia sarothrae	257
Agave palmeri	interactsWith	Opuntia engelmannii	201
Pinus edulis	interactsWith	Juniperus sp.	200

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Juniperus	199
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Opuntia phaeacantha	189
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Acacia greggii	170
Agave palmeri	interactsWith	Prosopis velutina	135
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Yucca baccata	133
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Prosopis velutina	130
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Quercus turbinella	124
Pinus edulis	interactsWith	Opuntia sp.	119
Pinus edulis	interactsWith	Quercus sp.	110
Agave palmeri	interactsWith	Dasyilirion wheeleri	109
Agave chrysantha	interactsWith	Eriogonum wrightii	109
Pinus edulis	interactsWith	Yucca sp.	109
Agave palmeri	interactsWith	Gutierrezia sarothrae	108
Agave verdensis	interactsWith	Opuntia phaeacantha	104
Agave palmeri	interactsWith	Fouquieria splendens	103

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at `indexed-interactions.csv.gz`. A tab-separated file can be found at `indexed-interactions.tsv.gz`

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Ft elev	NONE	col	Ft elev
Slopes formed sandstone residuum	NONE	col	Slopes formed sandstone residuum
Gramma grasses	NONE	col	Gramma grasses
Echinocarpa	NONE	col	Echinocarpa

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	38087
col	family	81
col	genus	1922
col	kingdom	2
col	order	3
col	phylum	2

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	section	2
col	species	15180
col	subfamily	2
col	subgenus	16
col	suborder	3
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	691
col	subterclass	1
col	superfamily	2
col	tribe	1
col	variety	443
discoverlife	NA	56095
discoverlife	species	2
gbif	NA	34612
gbif	family	90
gbif	form	19
gbif	genus	2126
gbif	kingdom	2
gbif	order	3
gbif	phylum	2
gbif	species	16740
gbif	subspecies	1361
gbif	variety	1943
itis	NA	40057
itis	class	1
itis	division	2
itis	family	85
itis	form	2
itis	genus	1667
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	5
itis	species	12652
itis	subgenus	2
itis	suborder	3
itis	subphylum	1
itis	subspecies	1018
itis	superfamily	1
itis	superorder	1
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	627
mdd	NA	56096
ncbi	NA	42044
ncbi	clade	2
ncbi	family	82

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
nbi	genus	1719
nbi	infraorder	1
nbi	kingdom	1
nbi	order	3
nbi	parvorder	1
nbi	section	2
nbi	species	12076
nbi	subgenus	11
nbi	suborder	2
nbi	subphylum	1
nbi	subspecies	82
nbi	superfamily	1
nbi	superorder	1
nbi	tribe	1
nbi	varietas	74
pdb	NA	55220
pdb	class	2
pdb	family	84
pdb	genus	590
pdb	informal	1
pdb	infraorder	1
pdb	kingdom	2
pdb	order	9
pdb	phylum	3
pdb	species	177
pdb	subclass	1
pdb	subfamily	1
pdb	suborder	3
pdb	superfamily	2
pdb	superorder	1
pdb	tribe	5
pdb	unranked clade	4
tpt	NA	56075
tpt	genus	19
tpt	order	1
tpt	species	1
wfo	NA	38323
wfo	family	79
wfo	form	3
wfo	genus	1747
wfo	phylum	3
wfo	species	15418
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	321

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
wfo	variety	361
worms	NA	52048
worms	class	1
worms	family	69
worms	genus	933
worms	kingdom	2
worms	order	3
worms	phylum	1
worms	phylum (division)	2
worms	species	2945
worms	subgenus	1
worms	suborder	3
worms	subphylum	1
worms	subspecies	63
worms	subterclass	1
worms	superfamily	1
worms	tribe	1
worms	variety	92

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	60411
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	69241
col	SYNONYM_OF	24482
discoverlife	NONE	142111
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	2
gbif	NONE	51720
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	89582
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	46517
itis	NONE	62119
itis	SYNONYM_OF	14020
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	68966
mdd	NONE	141957
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
ncbi	NONE	70562
ncbi	SAME_AS	65481
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	6777
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	90
pbdb	NONE	134495
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7531
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	314
tpt	NONE	141878
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	80
wfo	NONE	60784
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	68878
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	4579
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	18834
worms	NONE	118491
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	23122
worms	SYNONYM_OF	4618

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2025-04-13T15:54:50Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/seinet/archi
2025-04-13T15:54:50Z	summary	993128 interaction(s)
2025-04-13T15:54:50Z	summary	0 note(s)
2025-04-13T15:54:50Z	summary	64 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 5: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks

⁵At time of writing (2025-04-13) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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